

QUEEN MARIANA OF AUSTRIA AS REGENT AND THE BOUNDARIES OF HER POWER IN MAZO'S PORTRAIT

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During the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries, the Spanish crown was always worn by a male member of the Habsburg family. However important the position that a female member of the Royal Family occupied, be it as regent, governor or viceroy – and these positions were occupied by royal women on many occasions – they were always subordinated to a male figure. This state of affairs changed after the death of Phillip IV (1665), when the widowed Queen Mariana of Austria (1634–1696) became the sole regent for Charles II (1661–1700), who, besides being a child, also seemed mentally unfit to be king.

These events opened a new and unprecedented period in the history of the Spanish Habsburg. There were very few occasions when female royal figures played a public role in high politics; namely when their husbands were either absent or dead. It is noteworthy that in the latter case – i.e., when widows acted as regents for small children – restrictions to their power were vague and their guardianship over the heir was constantly threatened. In practice, this meant that queen regents had to carve their place on the political stage. This was the case with Mariana as she strived to create an image and a place for herself. As a widow her social life was over, according to the traditional concept of the institution of marriage. As a queen, however, her political life was – albeit temporarily – just beginning.

The Regency saw many a struggle between Mariana of Austria and certain aristocratic factions. Conflicts also arose between Mariana and the ambitious son of Philip IV and María Calderona, Don John Joseph of Austria. In these circumstances, it was crucial for the Regent to find ways of strengthening her position. As it happened, Mariana was remarkably successful: it can be safely stated that her Regency became the blueprint for all subsequent regencies. It is therefore not surprising that a new public image

Figure 1 Juan Bautista Martínez del Mazo, *Queen Mariana of Spain in Mourning*, 1666. Oil on canvas, 196.8 x 146 cm. National Gallery, London. © the National Gallery

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of Mariana had to be created, one that would be fit for a Queen under such special circumstances. In short, she had to re-invent her role and image in order to determine the way in which she was to be depicted for public consumption, particularly in her portraits.

The portrait introducing just such a new image of Queen Mariana as both ruler and guardian-tutor was painted by Juan Bautista Martínez del Mazo in 1666, during the first year of Royal mourning and entitled *Mariana in Mourning* (figure 1).¹ In the painting's foreground we see the Queen, seated on a chair with a dog lying at her feet, in the Alcázar in Madrid. Mariana's head seems to have been painted from life. She wears no make-up and is depicted dressed in the typical widow's attire of the period.²

Following Velázquez's *Las Meninas*, Mazo painted the group in the background including the King Charles II with a dwarf and one *menina*.³ The representation of one of the sculptures of the seven planets, Moon-Diana, indicates that the group is placed in the palace's Octagonal Room and also informs us that the Queen is shown in the adjacent Hall of Mirrors. The child King Charles II is performing a ceremony and there is a carriage nearby. The position of the child-king's body is unsteady: Mazo depicts Charles II in the traditional pose, holding a public audience, but in profile. His left leg is bent and his right leg is awkwardly bearing his weight. Charles did not start walking until he was four years of age, so a harness was used to help him stand up.⁴ The Queen's governess, Doña María Engracia de Toledo, Marquise of Vélez, and her daughter, lady-in-waiting to the King (who is proffering a clay vessel to him – another reference to *Las Meninas*), are in attendance. Another widow from the Queen's household and two dwarfs complete the group.⁵

The painting is not listed on any of the Alcázar's inventories (dating from 1666, 1686, and 1700), nor in that of Queen Mariana (dated 1696). However, we know from the Queen Mariana's inventory that Mazo's portrait of her daughter, Empress Margarita,⁶ which showed her in mourning for the death of her father, used to hang in the Palacio de Uceda. Critically, this painting is described as hanging in the room where the Queen 'used to eat',⁷ which would have functioned as a semi-public space. Therefore it can be conjectured that Queen Mariana's portrait could have been placed in a similar space.

Self-fashioning Queen Mariana as a widow

In the period that concerns us here, women's social identity was determined by three states: maidenhood, matrimony and widowhood. One of the most obvious ways to convey this state was through dress, which reflected and acknowledged social position. In this first portrait, Mariana is shown for the first time in her newly acquired state of widowhood, suggesting a reading of the painting as a ritual passage of status from Consort Queen to Widow Regent.⁸ Regarding widowhood, the contemporary Jesuit and religious writer, Father Astete, states that:

[...] it is an intermediate state between maidenhood and matrimony. It shares something with both, continence with the state of maidenhood, and the management of the household with matrimony. It is a more perfect state to remain a widow and not to marry again.⁹

The widow was supposed to forget her married life and give herself to chastity, fasting, prayer and the giving of alms in solitude: in becoming a widow, one became God's wife. The black dress sustained her chaste state and exemplary customs. Don Martín Carrillo, an abbot and religious writer, refers to the Biblical heroine Judith's exemplary widowhood by explaining that

[...] her attire in that period were not soft and precious silks, rich brocades, and fine cloth, but rather rough hair shirt and sombre mourning clothes, because the widow who wants to master the appetite of the senses and conquer it with her reason wears this kind of dress.¹⁰

So too proclaims Father Astete, for whom 'the outer dress should reveal the inner soul'; A similar view is held also by the author of the treatise *Carro de las Donas*: '(a widow) must leave behind all the dresses she wore as a married woman, for a man wants his wife to wear one sort of dress, and a different one of a different quality to be worn by the wife of Jesus Christ'.¹¹

In the painting, Queen Mariana is wearing her widow's attire, just as she was seen by a visitor, the Countess D'Aulnoy, on her tour of Spain. Describing her meeting with the Queen during her exile in Toledo, D'Aulnoy compares the Queen's attire to the way 'all the widows (in the

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nobility) dress in Spain; that is to say, like a nun, with not a single hair to be seen'.¹² The Countess gives a fuller explanation of a widow's dress by recalling when, on her travels to Madrid, she came across the Marquise de los Ríos, another widow who was on her way to a convent in order to spend the first years of her widowhood there. According to the Countess, the Marquise wore a black wimple, a black dress, a black batiste with no folds falling to below the knees, a black muslin veil covering her face, neck and hair, a black taffeta cloak down to her ankles and a black wide-brimmed hat with black ribbons, as worn by widows and virtuous women.¹³ However, the Queen does not wear a batiste and the muslin veil falling from her neck to below her waist is not black but white, following royal tradition.

That particular kind of widow's dress, a black dress generally made of low quality wool, was known as a *monjil*, because of its likeness to a nun's habit (from *monja*, nun). The *monjil* covered the whole body and was surmounted by a holland wimple.¹⁴ The black dress and cloak signified mourning, while the white colour of the long wimples alluded to the chastity of widowhood.¹⁵ The wimples were white because, according to Spanish custom, widows used the same veil as women who entered a nunnery, although the names differed: the latter's was called a conversion or simple veil, whereas the widows' veil was known as a continence or obedience veil.¹⁶

It is therefore Court etiquette and Spanish custom that dictate Doña Mariana's attire – the *monjil* is not, as other scholars have suggested, a Franciscan habit.¹⁷ In Mariana's case, the widow's habit stands for a reminder of her late husband, Philip IV, who had bestowed upon the Queen the legitimacy to carry out her tasks. It is also a symbol of faithfulness to her husband. In Tirso de Molina's play *La Prudencia en la Mujer* (1622), there is reference to the wimple as a symbol of authority and fidelity to a dead husband. Tirso has Doña María de Molina, Regent during the minority of her son Fernando, say the following words:

in sorrowful widowhood
 the most common woman
 the death of a most unjust husband
 mourns for a full year.

And later states:

Wimples in effect command,
 as the beard does in man,
 authority and respect.¹⁸

The rings Mariana of Austria is depicted wearing in the portrait are also important signs of her authority as Queen Regent. On her left ring-finger she wears what could be her wedding ring and, on her right thumb, what is possibly Philip IV's wedding ring.¹⁹ Queen Mariana is also holding a petition with her right thumb and forefinger which, as we shall see below, is a feature of the King's rule.

One account in the Royal Palace Archives, in Madrid, describes 'All that is necessary' for holding the *Wedding veiling ceremony*, a part of the wedding ceremony.²⁰ Among the required objects are the rings made of plain gold. These are identical to the two rings which embellish Mariana's hands. The presence of the two wedding rings points to a double reading: the authority of the reigning Regent derives from the fact that she was married to Philip IV and is the mother of Charles II. Furthermore, the rings reinforce the legitimacy of the Queen in the new role vested in her by her late husband's will and testament.

Pedro Calderón de la Barca's swashbuckling comedy, *La Dama Duende*, reflects on the harshness experienced by mourning widows at that time. In order to escape her imprisonment, Doña Angela, the heroine, has to change her mourning clothes for those of a marriageable woman and, on her return, has to change back into her widow's habit. She complains bitterly:

Give me back, Isabel,
 Those wimples, elusive sorrow!
 Give me back my living shroud
 For that is what my ill fortune
 Has decreed for me.

And later, Doña Ángela declares:

Heavens above! That I should
 Die within two walls
 Where the sun hardly enters
 (...)

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Where in effect imprisoned
 Without my freedom I have lived
 Because I became a widow.²¹

Women were expected to mourn their dead husbands and spend the first year of mourning in a room darkened with black drapes, where not even a single ray of sunlight was to be allowed in, sitting on holland covered cushions. After the first year they could move to another room with its walls covered in drapes of a somewhat lighter colour, but bereft of paintings and mirrors. The latter, together with silverware and fine pieces of furniture were meant to be of no use to widows. Widows were supposed, by force of a socially-produced mourning, to inhabit a world of withdrawal.²²

The painting that concerns us here was executed, as we have seen, during the first year of royal mourning. The Queen is portrayed sitting in the Hall of Mirrors, but there is not a single element in the painting that belongs to this room. Thus the remarkable lack of the contents of that highly symbolic room in the Alcázar in which the Queen had her portrait painted; the Queen's mourning may well be key to such a bare rendering of the room.

Social self-fashioning: depicting the new role of Doña Mariana

Mourning was a public show of piety. To shed tears for the death of one's husband was considered one of 'the accoutrements of a pious life', according to Luis Vives in his treatise *Tratado de la mujer cristiana*.²³ The franciscan Fransesc Eiximenes further develops these ideas in his book about women, *El Carro de las Donas*:

It is good and proper that a widow should mourn her husband and show the love she used to feel for him, how much he is going to be missed by his children and the solitude that awaits her. But this mourning must be done in moderation, not in excess, rather well contained, for t'is God who giveth and taketh away.²⁴

Grieving should be done in moderation for, as Luis Vives explains, 'there are two classes of grieving women, each of them equally at fault, albeit for different reasons: those who grieve too much and those who grieve too little'.²⁵

The former were at fault because they lack faith, while the latter betrayed the fact that their conjugal love was not great. Unlike either of them, the Queen is portrayed as one who weeps serenely for the loss of her husband. Also, since she appears alone in the foreground, distant from the other human figures, the painting seems to specifically convey the sense of the Queen's isolation and solitude.

Widows, as we have seen, had to mourn their husband's death in the first instance and then carry out his last will and testament. Mazo's portrait is, in this sense, a visual representation of the function that King Philip's testament bestows on the Queen. He vests in her the powers of guardian, carer and ruler of his children, his household and his realms:

And I withhold none of the powers that I have and that she should wield as guardian, carer and ruler: even if it be to make laws anew or amend them, and if it were necessary for such to be done, I confer upon her all the great power which vests in me for all that would be necessary and convenient [...] that she may do and act at will as necessary and convenient, but always taking counsel from the aforementioned Junta and not otherwise.²⁶

I would like to note here that Queens were usually aides to the King, never keepers of the household. But, in the state of widowhood, Doña Mariana has to take on the governance of the family. In the absence of her husband, she becomes the head of the family and is thus responsible for the management of the household.²⁷

It is important to individually consider the elements Mazo uses to depict the Queen as guardian, carer and ruler. Firstly there is the chair, which henceforth would be used to show that the Queen holds the powers of the King until the coming of age of her son. After Mazo's portrait, this feature – the Queen sitting on a chair – became common to all depictions of the Queen as ruler. Mariana is placed on the right of the portrait so that she is portrayed to the left of the child-King, as prescribed in the *Etiquetas Reales*, (the ceremonial book).²⁸ The chair is distinctive in that it is used to signify high status: Spanish women used to sit cross-legged on the floor, following Moorish custom, and royal queens and princesses were no exception.²⁹ As the Duke Antonio Gramont remarks in relation to his trip to Madrid in October 1659 in order to ask for infanta María Teresa's hand:

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the envoys are taken to Queen Mariana's rooms, where the infantas María Teresa and Margarita also are [...] now the three of them are on a carpeted dais, sitting under a canopy on divers cushions instead of chairs, one atop another. They all wear enormous overskirts [...] and it is with great difficulty that they all fit on the dais.³⁰

We also have Lady Fanshawe's account of her visit to the Queen at the Palacio del Buen Retiro in June 1664:

Her Majesty was at the end of the room, sitting on three cushions under the royal canopy, and the Empress on the left [...] Then Her Majesty asked me to sit, which I did on a cushion provided for this purpose. The other ladies sat down on a level lower than that of the senior maid, over whom no one but the Princesses have precedence.³¹

The Queen used the chair to eat at table and in certain ceremonies – as outlined by the *Etiquetas Reales* – but for the rest she followed Moorish custom. For the oath of the heirs to the throne the seating arrangements were as follows: 'the dais and steps are carpeted and, on top, next to the epistle, a large drape was placed for their Majesties, a chair for the King next to the Gospels, and four cushions for the Queen [...]'³² For theatrical performances, 'His Majesty's chair was placed on a carpet ... to the left of the Queen's cushions'.³³

Mazo thus portrays the Queen Regent as a ruler: she receives the Council of State just as her husband used to do every Friday – sitting on a chair. In a letter from Philip IV to his cousin, Princess Margarita, who was Governor of Portugal at the time, the King explains to her the new courtesies she had to observe as Portugal's Regent: she must sit in a chair placed on a high position.³⁴ We know from the courtesies of Juan José of Austria that a royal person used a velvet and fabric chair. In the painting the velvet is black, since the Queen was in mourning. The chair is an attribute of high status and the painting portrays the Queen discharging her duties as ruler.

The next feature that signals the Queen's new role as Regent is the petition that she is holding in her hand. One of the first things that Philip IV undertook immediately following his coronation was to reform the courtesies, cancelling all titles in the heading of a letter or document except 'Señor'.³⁵ Velázquez reflects this new bureaucratic activity of the young King

as well as the new moral climate in his *Philip IV* (1631–2). Mazo, following Velázquez, adds a petition which the Queen holds in her right hand addressed to ‘Señora’, a clear reference to Mariana. Also visible on the petition are ‘Juan Bautista del Mazo’, the painter’s signature and ‘1666’, the year in which the portrait was executed. Mazo thus identifies himself with the petitioner and with the author of the portrait, which is again a Velazquean convention.

The petition that Mariana is holding in her right hand is not only an attribute of royal iconography but also ‘indicates that in her house she takes better care of the needs of others than her own, we see her like God’s general treasurer, handing out her goods by her own hand’.³⁶ It also implies that the Queen performs her duties alone, without the need for a favourite, as decreed in her husband’s testament.³⁷ Finally, the dog lying at the Queen’s feet reaffirms Mariana’s faithfulness to Philip IV.

In the portrait, as mentioned above, Doña Mariana is shown in the Hall of Mirrors in the King’s apartments in the Alcázar.³⁸ However, it was not there that the Queen met the junta, but in a room inside the King’s palace next to his private Chambers. It is important to note that portraits of the Catholic monarchy, the ancestors of the Queen, used to hang in the Hall of Mirrors. But, as I have argued, what actually allows us to identify the place where the Queen is sitting for her portrait are not the contents and features of the Hall of Mirrors, but the Octagonal Room in the background,³⁹ with its distinctive Moon Diana sculpture, sent by Cardinal Infante to the King in 1637.⁴⁰

Mazo uses the lines of the black and white floor tiles to highlight the perspective that guides the eye of the observer from the drawn curtains on the door straight to the back of the picture. He offers a detailed description of the scene taking place in the background, behind Mariana, with bright, flat brush strokes. The use of the perspective leads the viewer’s gaze to the action in the background, but it is the viewer who has to link this to the portrait of the Queen Mother. This room, the scene where the King and other members of his household were portrayed, was part of the public apartments in the Alcázar. However, it is important to remark that the Queen and the boy king Charles II did not live in the King’s area of the palace, but in the Queen’s apartments.

Mazo covers the head of the *Moon-Diana* sculpture and plays with the opposition of the King as the Sun and the Queen as the Moon.⁴¹ One

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possible explanation for that is the mourning for the King. After Philip IV's death, everything in the Alcázar was covered in black cloth. This detail could thus symbolise the Queen's own grief in line with the tradition whereby for nine days following the death of the King Mariana, a thick black veil covering her head, would only grant an audience to women. It could well be then that the Moon, veiled as it is, and at whose feet is Charles II, ultimately alludes to the Queen, a star standing in the middle of two Suns.

This would echo the play on images in the King's exequies (funeral ceremony), which conveyed the sense, through the creation of various emblems, that the transference of power from Philip IV to Charles II necessitated an intermediate step, that of Mariana's regency. All of this found expression in the language of the stars, with a dying sun and a rising sun, with the moon (Mariana) in between the two. Until now, this planet has been mistaken for Venus. However, if we compare the sculpture painted by Mazo with the seven planets by Jacques Jonghelinck that are kept in the Palacio Real we will see that the sculpture portrayed in the painting is similar to the Moon-Diana statuette. If any of Jonghelinck's planets could adequately express one of the exequies' leit-motivs, i.e. the legitimacy of the Regency, it would be without any doubt the Moon.

It is also noteworthy that, since her arrival at court, Mariana had been alluded to by means of a lunar metaphor. In the Royal Exequies for Philip IV, held in the Monasterio de la Encarnación in October 1665, Hieroglyph No. 2 reads:

In the rays of the Moon
Another light burns bright
It is not night, tho' the Sun has died.

There are two suns in Hieroglyph No. 2, Philip IV and the little Charles II. The moon that protects the smaller sun is Mariana, who is to serve as Ruler Queen during Charles's minority. The Hieroglyph acknowledges the legitimacy of the succession (which proceeds in as regular and as orderly a fashion as day follows night) and the desirability of her regency.⁴²

Returning to Mazo's painting, the Moon-Diana is the Queen as ruler who takes care of the new child-King and safeguards the future of the monarchy. The young King playing in the Octagonal Room symbolises the idea of the

continuity of the Habsburgs. This room can be seen as a microcosm of the world, ruled by the planets just as the monarchs rule the real world. There were two more sculptures in the Octagonal Room: one of Charles V and the other of Empress Maria, who would later come to symbolise the Habsburg monarchy as the house that imposes order in the world.

The importance of the Octagonal Room is underlined by the presence of Charles II. As the new Sun, he is occupying the place that belongs to him in the natural order of things, in the middle of the universe surrounded by the planets. The idea that the Octagonal Room is a symbolic and privileged place for the monarchy can be inferred from an anecdotal account by Ludovico Incontri, the Florentine ambassador. According to this account, the King had decided to place a bureau and a gold equestrian statue given to him by the Grand Duke of Tuscany in 1651 in the Octagonal Room. According to the Ambassador, both the statue and the bureau are unique. The King had them placed in the Octagonal Room, which stands between two galleries, where it served as the King's tribune, the place where he kept his most precious treasures. In the King's presence, her Majesty the Queen and the Infanta were reckoning who would be entitled to them: the Queen wishing them for the first male born, and the Infanta for herself when she left His Majesty's house to marry. Merrily, the King told the ladies that they were wrong in their reckoning, since the horse and the bureau were placed in the Tribune, he was no longer their owner, as everything that was placed in the room was considered part of the Crown.⁴³ This meaning is closely related to the legal concept of *Guardian-tutor* or *Guardian-curador*, the role that Mariana had to take up after Philip IV's death.⁴⁴ In this role she had to look after the King and his territories, and was not allowed to dispose of his property, as Philip IV remarks in relation to the contents of the Octagonal Room. It is she who has to safeguard the monarchy until her son comes of age, whereupon she must transfer it to Charles in the same condition as Philip left it to her.

The Court was organised like a microcosm. The King was surrounded by his family, just like Infanta Margarita in *Las Meninas*.⁴⁵ There are some differences, however, between the family groups portrayed in these two paintings. In Mazo's painting, the artist depicts the changes that the minority of age of the King brings to the Court and the royal households and, by extension, to the servants and the King and Queen's 'extended family'.⁴⁶

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On Philip IV's death his household ceases to exist, as Luis de Moncada rightly says: 'there cannot be a King's household without a King, as [there cannot] be a living body without a soul', adding that

the house of HM is the house of the King our Lord, the true God, and there are no other representations, no other uses and no other servants' than those of Queen Mariana and the child king Charles II, and to deny this perfect principle is to go against the pre-eminence of the offices and servants of HM.⁴⁷

At that time, not only does some part of Philip IV's household disappear, but the Queen's household is also restructured, since it is not only the Queen's but also the child-king's, as he is a minor. The Queen's household was a closed world – access to it was controlled by the rules of etiquette. These were not modified, but new additions were introduced for Mariana.

In other words, those who wield power from 1665 onwards are those who are part of the Queen's household. Mazo underlines these changes, especially when he portrays only women next to the King, and then places them in an area of the palace from which they were normally barred, since this was the King's own area of the palace and part of the public apartments.⁴⁸

This was the first prototype of portraiture introduced at the beginning of the Regency. In the painting, Mazo depicted both the Queen's mourning and her new powers as ruler and Guardian-tutor. The painting reflects Mariana's newly acquired status of widowhood, her faithfulness to her dead husband, and the new powers she inherits in accordance with the royal will; as well as the temporary disappearance of part of Philip IV's household and the reorganisation of the Court around the Queen's household, whose members are seen surrounding the child king Charles II. The dual sources of her authority are reinforced as she is depicted both as Philip IV's widow and as mother of the future King.

Notes

I would like to thank Joseph L. Koerner and Charles Ford for their help and advice with my work.

- 1 The original painting is in the National Gallery, in London. There are two copies of this prototype, one in the Museo Casa Greco (Toledo, Spain) and the other in Museo de Arte de Ponce (Puerto Rico).

- 2 For a more detailed account of how the costume developed, see Carmen Bernis, 'El traje de viudas y dueñas en los cuadros de Velázquez y su escuela' in CSIC, Instituto Diego Velázquez, ed., *Miscelánea de Arte*, Madrid, 1982, pp. 145–152.
- 3 King, not Prince, since on 8 October 1665 flags flew over Madrid and other Castilian cities for Charles II.
- 4 On this subject we have Madame de Motteville's account of her visit to the *threshold* of the Infanta María Teresa's private chambers, from where she observes how respectfully the few who are allowed near her treat her: the page having to kneel in order to give a drink to a lady in order for her to hand it to the Princess, also kneeling, watched by a kneeling woman who hands her a serviette and a standing *Dama de Honor*. See Carl Justi, *Velázquez y su tiempo*, Madrid, 1999, pp.643–644.
- 5 In *Las Meninas* one of the ladies-in-waiting is tending a vase to the Infanta Margarita. In Mazo's painting, the King is holding a piece of paper in his right hand and with the left is taking the vase from the lady-in-waiting. His governess holds the harness with her right hand and the left one is tending an indistinguishable object.
- 6 In *La Emperatriz doña Margarita* (Museo del Prado, Madrid) the Empress-Infanta Margarita is shown in the foreground, dressed in black, her right hand on the back of a chair. In the background in another room, following the same composition as our painting, are Charles II, Mariana of Austria herself, a dwarf and a menina.
- 7 Antonio Rodríguez Villa, *Etiquetas de la casa de Austria*, Madrid, 1913, p.50.
- 8 Edward Muir, *Ritual in Early Modern Europe*, Cambridge, 1997, p. 27; Martine Segalen, *Ritos y rituales contemporáneos*, Madrid, 2005; Victor Turner, *The Ritual Process: Structure and Anti-structure*, New York, 1966.
- 9 Gaspar Astete, *Tratado sobre el gobierno de la familia y estado de las viudas y doncellas*, Burgos, 1603.
- 10 Martín Carrillo, *Elogio de mujeres fuertes del Viejo Testamento*, Huesca, 1627.
- 11 Francesc Eiximenis, *Este devoto libro se llama Carro de las donas, trata de la vida y la muerte del hombre cristiano...*, s.l., 1542.
- 12 Mme d'Aulnoy, *Viaje por España en 1679 y 1680*. Barcelona, 1962, pp.79–81; Carmen Bernis, op. cit., pp. 145–152; Ana García Sanz y Leticia Sánchez Hernández, 'Iconografía de monjas, santas y beatas españolas en los monasterios reales españoles' in *VIII Jornadas de Arte. La mujer en el arte español*, Madrid, 1996, p. 136. For the making of widow's attire, see Martín de Andújar *Geometría y trazas pertenecientes al oficio de sastres donde se contiene el modo y orden de cortar todo género de vestidos*, Madrid, 1640.
- 13 Mme d'Aulnoy, op.cit. pp. 79–81.
- 14 For a description of the *monjil*, see Alonso Castillo Solórzano, *Las Arpias en Madrid*, Pablo Jaural de Pou, ed., Madrid, 1980, p. 101.
- 15 Cristina Cuadra García y Ángela Muñoz Fernández, '¿Hace el hábito a la monja? Indumentaria e identidad religiosa femeninas' in Josemi Lorenzo Arribas and Ana Isabel Cerrada Jiménez, eds., *De los símbolos al orden simbólico femenino (ss. IV-XVII)*, Madrid, 1998.
- 16 Antonio León Pinelo, *Vélos antiguos y modernos en los rostros de las mugeres sus con veniencias y daños*, Madrid, 1641, p. 24.
- 17 Rosemary Marzolf, *The Art and Work of Juan Carreño de Miranda (1614–1685)*, Unpublished PhD thesis, University of Michigan, 1961, p 84. The Franciscan habit worn by Infanta Isabel Clara Eugenia in the Rubens portrait helps clarify this issue.

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- 18 Tirso de Molina's verses are quoted and analysed in Ruth Lee Kennedy, 'Las tocas en las comedias de Tirso, La prudencia en la mujer y La mujer que manda en casa: su valor simbólico', in Antonio González, T. Holzapfel and Antonio Rodríguez, eds., *Estudios sobre el Siglo de Oro en homenaje a Raymond R. McCurdy*, Madrid, 1983, pp. 206–209.
- 19 'Rings were worn especially nearest to the little finger of the left hand because of one of two reasons: either because the precious stone was less likely to come to harm or to be broken, or else because in that section of the human body anatomists had found a little delicate nerve that runs from that finger to the heart and along it the virtue of the gold as much as that of the precious stone could be conveyed and comfort it, Sebastián Covarrubias Orozco, 'anillo', in *Tesoro de la lengua castellana o español*, Madrid, 1611, p. 100. In the National Gallery original, the Queen wore two rings, one on her left ring finger and the other one on her right thumb. This ring has been eliminated during the National Gallery restoration process. The portrait copy in the Museo de Arte de Ponce preserves both.
- 20 It was traditional for the secretary or minister 'to present the wedding coins and two plain gold rings to HM's Keeper of the Jewels to be used when the time came together with the veil and the ribbon (...) in *Arras y anillos que se deben entregar por la secretaria del Despacho al guardajoyas para las velaciones de SS.MM.*, 1714, Madrid, Archivo General Palacio Real Madrid, Sección Histórica, expe.9.
- 21 Pedro Calderón de la Barca, *La dama duende*, Madrid, 1976.
- 22 d'Aulnoy, op. cit., pp. 79–81. The accounts of the Queen's Chamber confirm that, in effect, the rooms were initially decorated in black and later in gray, in half-mourning. *Tesorería de la Casa de la Reina*, unpublished documents, 1649–1696, Madrid, Archivo General Palacio Real Madrid, Sección Administrativa, cajas from 10.200 to 10.400.
- 23 Luis Vives, *La formación de la mujer cristiana*, Valencia, 1994, pp. 357–363.
- 24 Eiximenis, op. cit., p. 56.
- 25 Vives, op. cit., pp. 357–363.
- 26 *Testamento de Felipe IV*. Edición Facsimil, Introduction by Antonio Domínguez Ortiz, Madrid, 1982.
- 27 Astete, op. cit., p. 77.
- 28 *Etiquetas Generales*, unpublished manuscript, 1651, Madrid, Archivo General Palacio Real Madrid. Sección Histórica, caja 50.
- 29 Julián Gállego, *Visión y símbolos de la pintura española del Siglo de Oro*, Madrid, 1972.
- 30 Duque de Gramont, *Journal du Voyage d'Espagne*, Paris, 1669.
- 31 d'Aulnoy, op. cit., p. 159; see also Anne Fanshawe, *The Memoirs of Ann Fanshawe, Wife of the Right Honble Sir Richard Fanshawe*, London, 1907; Martin Hume, *Reinas de la España antigua*, Madrid, 1912, pp. 348–349.
- 32 Rodríguez Villa, op. cit., p. 142.
- 33 *Ibid.*, p. 79.
- 34 Dated November 1634: '(.) during an audience (...) the Marques of Puebla on a plain chair and the Secretary on a small stool'. *Instrucciones dadas a la Infanta Margarita al ser enviada por S.M. a Portugal en 1633, sobre el tratamiento y cortesías...*, unpublished manuscript, 1634, Madrid.
- 35 *Premática en que su Magestad manda que se guarden las que ultimamente se promulgarón (...)*, Madrid, 1636, unpublished manuscript, 1636, Madrid, Real Academia de la Historia;

- Pragmática Real sobre el tratamiento, y cortesías que se ha de tener [...]*, unpublished manuscript, Madrid, 1638.
- 36 Juan Zabaleta, *Errores celebrados*, Madrid, 1971.
- 37 The aristocracy criticised Mariana for having a favourite, betraying the wishes of the King. See Duque de Maura, *Vida y reinado de Carlos II*. Madrid 1942, vol. 3.; Duque de Maura, *Carlos II y su corte. Ensayo de reconstrucción biográfica*. Madrid, 1911, vol. 2.
- 38 Yves Bottineau, 'A portrait of Queen Mariana in The National Gallery' in *Burlington Magazine*, n° 97, 1955, pp. 114–116. Bottineau maintains that the Queen is shown in the Hall of Mirrors. The venue for the daily meetings of the ruling Junta was the Rubi room. See also Maura, op. cit., 146.
- 39 Bottineau, op. cit., pp. 114–116.
- 40 It has to be borne in mind that Philip IV was also known as the 'Sun King', hence the importance of the Planets and of the Octagonal Room, which symbolises the monarchy. Regarding the sending of the sculptures representing the Planets, see Carl Justi, op. cit.; Iain Buchanan, 'The Collection of Nicolaes Jongelincq: I. "Bacchus and the Planets" by Jacques Jongelincq' in *The Burlington Magazine*, no. 133 1990; Luc Smolderen, *Jacques Jongelincq: Sculpteur, médailleur, et graveur de sceaux (1530–1606)*, Louvain, 1996; Stephen N. Orso, *Philip IV and the Decoration of the Alcázar of Madrid*, New Jersey, 1978, also *Inventario de 1666*, unpublished manuscript, 1666, Madrid, Archivo General Palacio Real, Sección Administrativa, leg. 38 and Gloria Fernández Bayton, ed., *Inventarios Reales. Testamentaria del Rey Carlos II, 1701–1703*, Madrid, 1975.
- 41 According to Juan Pérez de Moya's *Philosophia secreta* the Moon 'is the name of the planet and of the woman who excels in some virtues or inventions in her time, (...) it is the name of light and clarity, (...)'. With regard to the Moon-Diana epithet, Pérez de Moya says: 'The Moon when waning is chaste, like Diana, for nothing is engendered during that time, (...) the Moon is chaste because of the influence of the cold and the wet, and the wet works against carnal communion; and because not having carnal desires is good for chastity, and this is the reason why the Moon or Diana, taken for her, keeps perpetual chastity, and was chaste. (...) It is said that Diana comes from *duana*, meaning two, in as much as it shines at two different times, during the day and during the night; or in as much as her light sometimes lasts until daytime' Juan Pérez de Moya, *Philosophia secreta*, Carlos Clavería, ed., Madrid, 1995.
- 42 Stephen N. Orso, *Art and Death at the Spanish Habsburg Court. The Royal Exequies of Philip IV*, Columbia, 1989, p. 83.
- 43 Miguel Morán Turina, 'Las estatuas del Alcázar. Notas sobre las colecciones escultóricas de los Austrias' in *El Real Alcázar de Madrid. Dos siglos de arquitectura y coleccionismo en la corte de los Reyes de España. Septiembre-noviembre, 1994*, exh. cat., Madrid, 1994, p. 259. Also Justi, op. cit., pp. 454–455; Jonathan Brown, *Velázquez, Painter and Courtier*, New Haven & London, 1986, p. 194.
- 44 To understand the terms Guardian-Tutor and Guardian-Curador see: Mercedes Llorente Molina, 'Mariana de Austria como gobernadora' in Jose Martínez Millán, ed., *Las Relaciones Discretas entre las Monarquías Hispana y Portuguesa: Las Casas de las Reinas (siglos XV-XIX)*, Madrid, 2008, pp.1777–1810.
- 45 Family are 'the people whom a man maintains in his household (...) man and wife, and the rest who are under his orders, such as children, servants, slaves', Sebastián

40 OBJECT

Covarrubias Orozco, 'familia', op. cit., 1611. On this theme, see Cesare Mozzarelli, *'Familia' del principe e famiglia aristocratica*, Roma, 1988. Fernando Marías, ed., *Otras Meninas*, Madrid, 1996 and Fernando Marías, *Velázquez. Pintor y criado del rey*, Madrid, 1999.

46 Marías, op. cit., p. 43.

47 *Sobre lo que tengo representado ala Ray^a nra S^a en mi consulta tocante a la entrada [...]*, unpublished document dated October 22nd 1665, Madrid. Archivo General Palacio Real Madrid, Sección Administrativa, legajo 623.

48 Visits to the child king were governed by the rules of etiquette, and they could only be carried out in his mother's chambers.